

THE MANIFESTATION OF MOTIVATION TO AVOID FAILURES IN THE PRACTICE OF GENERAL PRACTITIONERS

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of a study of the motivational sphere of general practitioners with different levels of organizational skills.*

Keywords: *motivation to achieve success, motivation to avoid failure, fear of implementation, organizational skills.*

Training specialists in the field of medicine is one of the complex organizational tasks of society. General practitioners are specialists who are familiar not only with modern diseases, but also with new technologies and the new medical equipment industry. A general practitioner is not only a person who knows how to find an approach to different segments of the population, but also a competent specialist who knows which medication can affect the disease and will not harm the health and general psycho-emotional state of the patient.

The management of medical personnel is entrusted to the head physician of the institution. Strict subordination and hierarchy of relations in the team of medical workers creates specific management relations. However, the expansion of the network of private medical institutions in market conditions restructures the relationship between the patient and the doctor. Medical care turns into medical services. In such conditions, without basic education of a manager, doctors make mistakes in their professional activities. Namely, in management, imposing your services is a good marketing move, while in medicine, imposed treatment does not always have a positive result. A patient who does not agree with the treatment, but, in the end, overcame the disease is still grateful to the doctor, while the erroneous opinion that for his money the client can dictate his terms continues to be cultivated. Especially in the beauty industry, surgical interventions and even obstetrics. The task of a modern therapist is to form in the patient the correct, competent, psychologically and legally correct idea regarding his health and methods of its restoration. Of course, we are talking about the motivational sphere of the therapist. His values and personal maturity are not always a field for assessing him as a professional. It is not necessary to be friendly if you are a good surgeon, but a therapist is required to have developed communication skills and organizational abilities. Is a modern therapist really a manager who plans the patient's actions taking into account the correct risk prognosis and the presentation of options for solving health problems? What is the payment for medical services? For time? For a diagnosis? For the result of treatment or for the scientific level of a specialist? Consumers of medical services still do not know about this. The development of management in medicine is an open question that requires a solution. In the course work, we only outlined this problem of organizational psychology.

Motivation to achieve success is the engine of developing relationships and professional growth. Whereas the expectation of failure leads to a limitation of the search for solutions to the patient's problems and issues.

The aim of the study is the study and identification of the characteristics of motivation to avoid failure among general practitioners.

The hypothesis of the study is the assumption that the motivation to avoid failure is more often manifested in doctors with low levels of organizational skills.

Experimental model for studying the motivational sphere of subjects. At the first stage of the study, indicators of the development of organizational skills necessary for performing professional activities were identified. The description of the methodology is presented in Appendix 1. Based on the testing results, two groups of subjects were identified - therapists. The first group consisted of subjects with high indicators of development of leadership skills. The second group consisted of subjects with low leadership skills. At the second stage, the motivation to achieve success and avoid failure was studied. In our opinion, the activities of a therapist require the presence of motivation for achievement in combination with professional skills. The therapist must be able to direct the patient and orient him or her toward effective treatment. Motivation not only determines human activity, but also permeates most areas of psychological activity. In the research, we studied the indicators by which judgments are made about the qualitative or quantitative characteristics of motivation, presented in Table 1.

"Indicators of qualitative or quantitative characteristics of motivation"

Table No. 1

Motivation indicators	People who are focused on avoiding failure	People who are focused on achieving success
Direct assessment of a person's ideas about the causes or characteristics of behavior, interests, etc.	They blame everyone (externality), they blame only themselves.	They are characterized by the search for information to judge their successes, the willingness to accept responsibility. They are confident in a successful outcome. They show great persistence when faced with an obstacle.
The influence of motives on cognitive assessments.	Subjective assessment, low understanding of the objectivity of the situation, sees the result and not the process	great persistence in striving for a goal, they get increased pleasure from interesting tasks, super-complex or simple tasks do not arouse enthusiasm in them
Identification of the zone of goals relevant to the motive.	The zone is narrowed. Low frustration tolerance	
Perseverance when faced with an obstacle.	Minimal. Abandonment of goals. Fixation on an obstacle with an impunities type of response	
Identification of a set of internal or external barriers	Internal barriers. Abandonment of goals.	In competitive situations they do not get lost.

Decision-making time in a motivational conflict of choice of alternatives.	Thinks for a long time	Depending on the situation and complexity of the tasks
Time parameters: amount of time - real time distribution amount of time - desired time allocation the amount of time a person spends discussing	Spends a lot of time discussing reasons, looking for the guilty and discussing the difficulty of the tasks at hand. Constant lack of time. Lack of composure. Desire to kill time.	Discussion of reasons and search for factors that eliminate them. Search for prospects for solving problems and competent people. Effective time management.
Evaluation of effective performance of activities	prefer to take on either very easy tasks or very difficult ones, since choosing easy tasks guarantees success to him, and the choice of very difficult tasks does not cause him great distress. Because failure in this situation does not give him a reason for shame and a sense of humiliation.	prefer to choose tasks of average difficulty, or slightly above average difficulty; they are attracted to situations of achievement.
Identification of the personal meaning of various characteristics of behavior, activity, situation	Personal meaning has its own prestige and sense of dignity.	Characterized by a desire for reasonable risk. They have a medium or high realistic (adequate) level of aspiration. They increase their level of aspiration after success, and decrease it after failure.
Typical defense mechanisms that can be associated with motives and needs.	displacement	Rarely connected
Free associations	Associations are connected with emotions and difficulties. Depressive in nature.	Association of Prospects
Observing the behavior of others: a) in a simulated situation, b) in a natural setting	Assesses others as luckier and more successful.	Evaluates himself, not others. Accepts competition with respect.

The nature and intensity of emotional reactions, determination of current motivation	The attitude towards oneself is inadequately overestimated self-esteem. Emotional response to the discrepancy between the intended and realized plan.	Characterized by a desire for reasonable risk. They have a medium or high realistic (adequate) level of aspiration. They increase their level of aspiration after success, and decrease it after failure.
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The motivation indicators described in the table will be analyzed in conjunction with the obtained research results.

Diagnostics of the characteristics of the motivation to avoid failures of subjects

Of the 34 subjects, 10 were selected with pronounced indicators of abilities and 10 subjects with low indicators of organizational abilities.

Description of the results of the first group. Quantitative data are reflected in table No. 2.

"Ability indicators. Average indicators n = 10".

Table No. 2

No.	Ability indicators	balls	rank	Motivation n = 10	
1	Ability to manage oneself	10	1	Achievement motivation	Failure Avoidance Motivation
2	Clear values	10	1	8	2
3	Clear personal goals	9	2		
4	Continuous self-development	9	2		
5	Good problem-solving skills	9	2		
6	Creative approach	9	2		
7	Ability to influence others	10	1		
8	Understanding the specifics of managerial work	8	3		
9	Ability to lead	7	4		
10	Ability to teach	8	3		
11	Ability to organize group work	7	4		
Σ		96			

The subjects of this group have high rates of development of organizational skills $\Sigma = 96$. The subjects are able to manage themselves, with a developed value system (to achieve success in solving a problem), they know how to influence others (due to their professional position and opinion of a specialist regarding a problem). Personal goals are to achieve goals, ongoing self-

development, good problem-solving skills, a creative approach against the background of a well-developed understanding of the peculiarities of managerial work and the ability to teach. The subjects are able to manage and have the ability to establish group work. The subjects of this group have the goal in their medical practice when working with patients to "manage" - direct joint activities to implement a treatment program. The most important thing is the moral side of the work. Namely, the goal of treatment is not to launch drug programs, but to launch a program of joint work to solve a problem situation, treat a disease and remove its negative consequences. The therapist's actions are collegial, collaborative, with professional consulting. 80% out of 100% of subjects have developed achievement motivation (see Table 1, p. 2.1.)

Success-oriented subjects prefer to choose tasks of average difficulty or slightly above average difficulty; they are attracted to achievement situations. They are confident in a successful outcome. They are characterized by the search for information to judge their success, readiness to accept responsibility, great persistence in striving for a goal, they get increased pleasure from interesting tasks, super-complex or simple tasks do not cause them enthusiasm. In competitive situations, they do not get lost. They are characterized by a desire for reasonable risk. They have an average or high realistic (adequate) level of aspiration. They increase their level of aspiration after success, and decrease it after failure. They show great persistence when faced with an obstacle.

Description of the results of the first group. Quantitative data are reflected in table No. 3.

"Ability indicators. Average indicators n = 10"

Table No. 3

No.	Ability indicators	balls	rank	Motivation n = 10	
1	Unable to control themselves	5	6	Achievement motivation	Failure Avoidance Motivation
2	Clear values	8	3	3	7
3	Clear personal goals	9	2		
4	Halted self-development	5	6		
5	Good problem-solving skills	7	4		
6	Creative approach	8	3		
7	Ability to influence others	10	1		
8	Lack of understanding of the specifics of managerial work	4	7		
9	Ability to lead	6	5		
10	Ability to teach	7	4		
11	Ability to organize group work	8	3		
Σ		77			

The subjects of this group have high rates of development of organizational skills $\Sigma = 77$. This is the average level of development of organizational skills. High rates of the ability to influence others were revealed. Clear goals are defined (the patient's orientation to purchasing the drug), personal interest in earning money, explanation through values (education of children, family expenses), the ability to organize work in a group with a bright creative approach is

developed (often frightening the patient in case of refusal of the drug, intimidating the patient, influencing value attitudes, intimidating relatives of patients, shifting responsibility from the patient to relatives), refers patients to doctors they know, and not to specialists in the profile. It demonstrates problem-solving skills and shows how to teach. The subjects of this group are not focused on working on professional growth and self-development. In the case of an obstacle and a threat to authority, doubts about professionalism, control over emotions does not work. These subjects are unable to manage themselves. Low management ability, ignorance of management problems. 70% of subjects expressed motivation to avoid failures. The signs are described in Table 1, paragraph 2.1. Subjects who are focused on avoiding failures prefer to take on either very easy tasks or very difficult ones, since choosing easy tasks guarantees success, and choosing very difficult tasks does not cause them much grief, because failure in this situation does not give them a reason for shame and a sense of humiliation. The main goal is to achieve material gain.

The study shows the presence of discrepancies in the indicators of self-management, self-development. Understanding the essence of the leader's activities. High skill in management activities. Difference in the goals of achievement. It is the difference in goals and their "dishonesty, falsity" that makes one experience fear of exposure and, accordingly, the program of testing a negative feeling of failure is connected. This is clearly manifested in the medical profession.

Conclusions

The study of achievement motivation does not in itself determine the specifics of individual professional behavior.

The study of managerial abilities in the case of the activities of general practitioners determines the basic essence of motivational structures and their impact on the effectiveness of professional implementation.

The experiment showed that the basis of the motivational structure is occupied not only by certain motivation indicators, but also by the goals of the activity. In the first case, in the group with high organizational abilities, the goal of the activity is professional realization (achieving a result is an effective way of treating and overcoming problems). In the group with low indicators of organizational abilities, the goal is selling drugs, material incentives.

In the first group, the motivation is to achieve and express all indicators and indices. At the same time, there is a tendency towards self-development and increased personal growth. In the second case, the motivation is to avoid failures and all the consequences associated with this direction, up to professional degradation.

The hypothesis that failure avoidance motivation is more common in physicians with low organizational skills has been tested, but research on a representative sample is needed to explain it.

In the group of subjects with different manifestations of organizational abilities, a difference in the goals of achievement is highlighted. It is the difference in goals and their "vagueness, falsity" that makes one experience fear of exposure and, accordingly, the program of testing the negative feeling of failure is activated. This is clearly manifested in the medical profession of subjects with low organizational ability.

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